

Newsletter Year 1 January 2024

EDGE **A-IQ READY**

A-IQ Ready

Artificial Intelligence for Realtime Distributed Systems at the Edge

A-IQ Ready project aims to introduce and materialise an intelligent autonomous ECS fit for our digital age and utilise crucial technologies, like edge continuum orchestration for artificial intelligence, distributed collaborative intelligence and quantum sensing, which could prove revolutionary for most services and industries. These technologies and their combination will propel the transition to a Europe of Society 5.0.

Inside this Issue

About 2
Project Structure 3
Interview with A-IQ Ready Coordinator Darjan Kozic 4
Project Technical Achievements 5
A-IQ Ready at Meetings/Conferences 10
Opcoming Events 11
A-IQ Ready Consortium 12

Project coordinator:

Dr. Darjan Kozic
AVL List GmbH

Participating organizations:

50

Project start:

01.01.2023

Duration:

36 months

Requested EU contribution:

~€M 10,6

Total investment:

~€ 33,7 M

Number of countries

15

About

A-IQ Ready Vision

The onset of climate change and widespread geopolitical conflicts and social inequalities showcase the need for innovation and change that require a better world. Now technologies like artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, robotics and other related technologies are making such a world all the more feasible.

The A-IQ Ready project aims to introduce and materialise an intelligent autonomous ECS fit for our digital age and utilise crucial technologies, like edge continuum orchestration for artificial intelligence, distributed collaborative intelligence and quantum sensing, which could prove revolutionary for most services and industries. These technologies and their combination will propel the transition to a Europe of Society 5.0.

A-IQ Ready addresses two major Trends: "Internet of Things (IoT) with 1 Billion \$ to 1 Trillion \$ revenues" and "From Cloud to Edge". A-IQ Ready will apply three disruptive technologies: Quantum Sensor, Neuromorphic Acceleration, AI in Multi-Agent Systems to build the edge continuum as the digital backbone for the Society 5.0.

Figure 1. A-IQ Ready vision.

A-IQ Ready Objectives

- O1: Improve sensing accuracy, reliability and trustworthiness in complex environments with new multi-physics (quantum) sensor
- O2: Build AI methods for multi-agent autonomy in uncertain environments
- O3: Provide a reference open AI Edge Continuum platform integrating quantum sensors, neuromorphic (cognitive) computing and AI algorithms at the edge
- O4: Demonstrate the approach to build the digital society
- O5: Increase Europe's competitiveness in developing a safe, resilient and prosperous digital society

Project Organisation

The A-IQ Ready project is organized in Work Packages (WPs) and Supply Chains (SCs). WPs represent the R&D domains with a focus on technologies and methodology, while SCs represent real implementation, demonstrators, experimental work, and implementation efforts leading to the integration of the (sub)systems and their verification and validation.

A-IQ Ready has eight Wps. WP1 defines the system requirements as well as the use cases and validation methodologies, also making sure research results of A-IQ Ready are aligned with targets set by the Green Deal, Ethics guidelines, and upcoming standards, which are relevant for AI and shared connectivity. WP2 is dedicated to the system level design based on modelling and simulation of several architectures for intelligent automated vehicles with the purpose of providing cost-efficient and reliable solutions to the market. WP3 will evaluate and design the semiconductor devices and modules for subsystems and systems to support the demonstrators in all SCs. WP3 also includes qualification related topics especially stress conditions specific for automotive and industrial applications are considered. WP4 covers the development of AI based and cognitive embedded systems and computing algorithms.

WP5 cares about the system integration for all supply chains. Within the frame of WP6 validation and testing of the SC demonstrators takes place. It focuses on reliability validation of the developed subsystems with the goal to demonstrate the properties and performance of the developed solutions in relation to the requirements defined in WP1. WP7 covers exploitation, dissemination, standardization and market trends monitoring to analyse the solutions developed by competitors. WP8 performs the overall project management, including monitoring and all financial & contractual aspects.

The idea of eight A-IQ Ready SCs is to group research activities around common topics. SC1 to SC4 are "output enabler", focusing on topics with a higher part of integration work. SC5 to SC7 are "Technology Fields", dealing with more basic technology development and research. SC8 finally binds the project to the concepts of novel emerging technologies. It achieves this by working with the other SCs on their requirements, system design, and validation phases.

Figure 2. A-IQ Ready matrix structure.

Interview with A-IQ Ready Coordinator Darjan Kozic

Darjan Kozic
AVL List GmbH
July 2023

1. Can you tell us a bit about how and when the inspiration for the A-IQ Ready project came about?

The time during the pandemic and initiation of the war has revealed the issues which require solutions so that Europe can become strong, autonomous and resilient. The disruption of supply chains has shifted the economic center of gravity from the West to Asia. At this stage, the European eco-system of politics, economy, industry and research has launched initiatives to work on solutions to overcome those challenges.

2. And what does the name of the project, A-IQ Ready, represents?

The name of the project represents the three main pillars of technological development in the A-IQ Ready project: Quantum sensing, Edge continuum orchestration of AI, Distributed collaborative intelligence. The development and complementation between those three technology pillars shall return a successful project outcome as well as reach the ultimate goal of an autonomous, sovereign and resilient Europe, so that the provision of goods and services to the European society becomes less dependent on uncontrollable factors.

3. What is the greatest ambition for A-IQ Ready?

In my opinion, the greatest ambition for A-IQ Ready is to reveal again the innovative European spirit to create a new way of leveraging information and use it in different domains for effective monitoring, maintenance, and development of technologies for a safe, secure, independent and resilient European economy and digital society.

4. A-IQ Ready addresses two major Trends: "Internet of Things (IoT) with 1 Billion \$ to 1 Trillion \$ revenues" and "From Cloud to Edge". Can you tell us a bit more about it?

To achieve the problems of our time such as climate change and relieving the life of individuals in a fast-paced society and environment, stakeholders are investing more and more into accelerating technologies

to fulfill those goals: Data acquisition technologies, AI technologies, and computation technologies. And all of this is to innovate new IoT devices and increase the capabilities of IoT devices. The idea "From cloud to Edge" shall facilitate this growing demand on IoT services by distributing the duties to different devices or agents along the way, creating an Edge continuum towards the Cloud and back. In this way, the expected real-time information required for further utilization can be leveraged at different stages by the user to improve latency, reliability, and security along the way.

5. What is expected impact of A-IQ Ready be on European society and worldwide?

The expected impact on European society should be to relieve the everyday life of the general population so that each individual is able to focus on becoming creative and thoughtful again about the environment and how we want to shape the future of society. The solutions from A-IQ Ready can have the same impact worldwide, especially in countries that are further away from the realization of the so-called digital society 5.0. In this sense, we additionally have to look beyond the proposed achievements from A-IQ Ready and think about what needs to be done to achieve that. The project A-IQ Ready shall provide the basis for that.

6. What is your wish for the first year of the project and for the A-IQ Ready consortium?

My wish is that each individual member of the consortium feels comfortable and home in the project. Each partner shall know that no matter how big or small its contribution is, every specific part is meaningful and provides a puzzle piece to the success of A-IQ Ready.

Project Technical Achievements

sci-sc8

Safe Co-Existence of Automated and Manual Transport at Industrial Sites

SCI

The Kouvola case is about automating container loading and unloading to/from rail wagon with a reach stacker, complemented with autonomous container transport with an autonomous terminal tractor, see Figure 4. During the first year the actions were condensed into three use cases, the related requirements were defined, and the preliminary safety analyses were carried out.

The Rauma case is about automating log transport within a sawmill area. More practically it is about transferring log cages between various loading and unloading locations. The transfer will be carried out by an AGV -like heavy vehicle, which can change its ground clearance by over 30cm, allowing it to lift a log cage on its 'shoulders' for transportation, and leave the log cage on the ground by 'kneeling' down again, see Figure 5. During the first year all the AGV actions were condensed into one transport use case, the related requirements were defined, and the preliminary safety analyses were carried out.

Figure 4. Machine types involved in the Kouvola case. On the top – reach stacker for loading/unloading containers to/from rail wagons. On the bottom – terminal tractor for the horizontal transportation of containers.

Figure 5. The AGV -like heavy vehicle involved in the Rauma case, visualised in its planned operations. On the top, AGV in low height driving carefully under a log cage before raising to normal height. On the bottom, AGV in normal height transferring the log cage to a new location.

In A-IQ Ready SC2 focuses on Search & Rescue (SAR) and emergency response for civil safety and especially on the localization in GNSS-denied environments. SC2 will implement its findings on a dedicated SAR demonstrator, which will be developed with the supporting methodology in simulation. Based on AI methods and dedicated perception sensors, a survivor detection will be performed. The quantum sensor itself is developed in SC5.

In the middle of June, SC2 partners met in the first F2F meeting organized at Zentrum am Berg, Austria. The main goals of the meeting were to discuss individual status, progress in the ongoing tasks and get knowledge of the tunnel facilities where the final demonstrations of SC2 are planned.

By the end of this meeting, three use cases dedicated to the localization and mapping of a single robot (real-world), a multi-robot (simulation) system and the wireless communication in a tunnel were defined. Over the course of the first year, a high-level concept for each use case as well as requirements were developed.

Figure 6. SC2 partners @Zentrum am Berg.

Digital Health and Emergency Recognition for Driver and Operator

The majority of traffic accidents are caused by factors such as driver's low attention level, speeding, and disobeying traffic regulations. Therefore, it's necessary to introduce active safety measures and technologies that reduce dangers on the roads caused by human error. Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) are already implemented in all modern vehicles with the purpose of introducing higher comfort and safety in the traffic. SC3's focus is "Digital Health and Emergency Recognition," where partners are contributing to development of such systems aiming to effectively monitor drivers' attentiveness and anticipate driver drowsiness.

During the initial year of the project, partners involved in SC3 have aligned the fundamental framework for three different use cases, all aimed at the shared objective of monitoring driver's condition. The final agreement on the demonstrators was reached during the General Assembly meeting held in Barcelona in October. These three use cases are currently under development, with partners already actively contributing with their findings and results.

Figure 7. Experimental activity for sleep prediction and emotional state analysis based on physiological data.

Figure 8. Demonstrator vehicle will be equipped with necessary HW and SW components for driver's state estimation.

The main achievement was the completion of the requirements and specifications. MBAG provided required for automotive applications and a benchmark Integrated Hall-Sensor approach. This can be used to compare the Q-Sensor solution.

AVL provided a design for the required e-Machine and the corresponding design simulations so that the e-Machine can be constructed. AVL will additionally provide the plans for e-Machine production. Within UC03 AVL will be able to provide a methodology performing monitoring actions, predictive warnings and derating functions for more reliable and safe propulsion systems.

BUT added requirements on distributed diagnostic system of the powertrain were defined. Defined requirements will serve for further development of methods and algorithms for fault diagnostics with the help of quantum flux sensor. The plan is to demonstrate as uses case 02 an example of the on-the-edge diagnosis as well as the example where HPC system is involved in data processing.

Figure 9. Architecture of the flux-based control.

Figure 10. Sketch of UC03.

Quantum Sensor Multi-Modal, Multi-Physical Sensing at Highest Precision

SC5

A-IQ Ready SC5 deals with major challenges in providing quantum sensors enabling ultra-precise low dynamic range (Earth's magnetic field) and ultra-fast high-dynamic range magnetic field measurements (in the context of motor control applications). Project partners: Institute of Electronics and Computer Science (EDI), Arquimea Research Center (ARQ) and Friedrich-Alexander-University (FAU) aggregated sensor requirements and developed system architecture of the sensor (sensor head, readout electronics, optics). The envisioned system supports ODMR, RF/light-modulated lock-in and pulse-based measurement methods. Further, ARQ and FAU created the first sensor head designs and managed to acquire initial ODMR spectra. The team is currently finalizing the first iteration of the readout/control electronics, designing an RF "antenna" for enabling energy-efficient high dynamic range measurements and fabricating the next iteration of the small <math><1\text{cm}^3</math> sensor head.

Figure 11. Quantum sensor research.

Hybrid Computing

SC6

In SC6, the development focusses on providing hardware and software platforms to enable integration of new multi-modal sensors into complex hybrid computing platforms. The enhancement will foster the enablement of intelligence at the sensor and SC6 will investigate multi-grain reconfigurable overlay architecture integrated in a RISC-V processor. Furthermore, the work will realize an acceleration platform whose operational envelope can be tailored to the varying requirements of device types across the sensor cloud value chain.

Cooperative Multi-Agent Systems (decentralized AI for emergent industrial solutions)

SC7

Supply Chain 7 focuses on advancing the way industrial mobile robots operate in industrial environments for goods transportation by employing advanced AI techniques, aiming for superior performance over traditional methods. The first year of A-IQ Ready involved defining requirements for the two demonstrators of supply chain 7 and starting with the development of the corresponding solutions. The central innovative element is the adoption of reinforcement-learning-based control for AGVs in real environments. The first year culminated in the agreement on the two demonstrator concepts among all involved partners. Progress includes the development of the AI algorithms on prototype level, building the AGV interfaces to actually control real AGVs on the shop floor, shipping of the AGVs, developing of a virtual training platform with cutting-edge physics and rendering, the development of models that ensure safe training of reinforcement-learning based agents, as well as a software for advanced monitoring purposes. These components are set for implementation in the demonstrators in the upcoming year.

Figure 12. SAFELOG AGVs transporting goods in the industry 4.0 platform proto_lab.

AI, Architectures, Tools and Methodologies (for open source and cross domain fertilization)

SC8

To achieve the objective of providing AI methods for multi-agent autonomy in uncertain environments, SC8 started to explore modular approaches for AI-based computation. By breaking down complex AI models into smaller, efficient components and deploying them on edge devices, the overall project aims to enhance scalability, flexibility, and resource optimization in AI computations. The focus will be on adapting these modular approaches to handle the challenges of uncertain environments and validating their effectiveness.

Accordingly, SC8 started the process for collecting and aggregating requirements from all Supply Chains and related Work Packages with respect to the defined 8 Concepts for creating a novel multi-modal sensor technology platform and architecture. SC8 will consider that the platform should seamlessly integrate diverse sensor types and modalities, enabling advanced data collection and fusion capabilities. With respect to the different angles and targets of the "Output Enabler" (SC1-SC4) and "Technology Provider" (SC5-SC7) SC8 integrate all requirements and input to detail the A-IQ Ready Concepts which are supposed to serve as kind of a guardrail for the different use cases and demonstrators.

Figure 13. Concepts of the A-IQ Ready project.

A-IQ Ready at Meetings/Conferences

A-IQ Ready General Assembly Meeting

On the 10th–11th of October 2023, A-IQ Ready partners had the great pleasure of meeting at the first General Assembly Meeting, which was organized in Barcelona, Spain. A two-day event was dedicated to aligning the project status and next steps to finalize the first year of the project successfully.

The meeting started with Core team discussions, contractual aspects, WPs' and SCs' status updates, main challenges, and future plans. The first day of the Meeting was especially productive and beneficial for A-IQ Ready SCs, because they had a chance to dedicate the afternoon to round tables – workshops and align on ongoing tasks, concrete use cases, and following activities. On the second day of the Meeting, SCs' and WPs' leaders presented the final status updates and conclusions of yesterday's workshops. Thanks to all partners for coming, for participating and active discussions!

Figure 14. A-IQ Ready General Assembly Meeting.

A-IQ Ready at The Autonomous

On the 14 th of September 2023, A-IQ Ready project was presented at the Autonomous Main Event, where Reiner John from AVL gave the project related presentation at the the spotlight session - Autonomous Driving and Future Mobility Trends in R&D.

This session hosted by TTTech Auto focused on the rapidly evolving fields of autonomous driving and future mobility technologies. It aimed to address key challenges such as as precise localization, sensor integration, intelligent decision-making, and distributed collaborative intelligence. The workshop aimed to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing among experts, researchers, industry professionals, and policymakers to explore innovations and opportunities in this domain. In this session, Reiner John shared his insights about sustainable mobility and technology convergence, specifically the synergies it takes to transform our ecosystems towards autonomous vehicles. He stressed the importance of collaboration, not just on a technological level, but also on a societal level, reminding the audience that the acceptance of a new technology largely depends on the value it contributes to a community. Reiner John illustrated how the A-IQ-Ready project contributes to this objective by applying disruptive technologies, such as Quantum Sensing, Neuromorphic Acceleration, and AI in multi-agent systems to build up a digital backbone for the Society 5.0.

Figure 15. A-IQ Ready at the Autonomous.

A-IQ Ready at Chips JU Launch Event

On the 20th November – 1st December, 2023 A-IQ Ready project was presented at the Chips JU Launch event, at "Walk of Fame" exhibition in Brussels, where A-IQ Ready project had a joint booth with already finalized NewControl project. As several A-IQ Ready SCs continues research of the NewControl project, A-IQ Ready project stands as NewControl project continuation. Implementing the continued research, A-IQ Ready aims to introduce and materialize an intelligent autonomous ECS fit for our digital age and utilize crucial technologies, like edge continuum orchestration for AI, distributed collaborative intelligence, and quantum sensing.

Figure 16. A-IQ Ready at Chips JU Launch event.

At all, more than 800 participants joined the event to mark the official inauguration of the Chips Joint Undertaking, insightful discussions, and networking. A series of introductory speeches and panel discussions featuring CEOs, CTOs, and other high-level Public Authorities illuminated the multifaceted challenges and opportunities in chip technologies and in the overall electronic components and systems sector.

Day two shifted focus to the Chips for Europe Initiative, revealing its multifaceted nature through detailed presentations and discussions. The audience had the opportunity to get into topics like advanced pilot lines, competence centers, cutting-edge quantum chips.

Overall, this Chips JU Launch event not only served as an arena for the discourse on future strategies and innovations in the semiconductors domain in Europe, but it also evolved into a dynamic networking hub, fostering the creation of new RD&I connections and the fortification of existing ones.

Upcoming Events 2024

- | | |
|---------------|---|
| 12–15 May | ISOEN 2024 – The IEEE International Symposium on Olfaction and Electronic Nose
isoen2024.org |
| 2–5 June | IEEE IV 2024 – 35th IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium
ieee-iv.org/2024/ |
| 15–19 July | IEEE EMBS – 46th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society
embs.org/2024/ |
| 1–4 September | EUROSENSORS XXXVI
akcongress.com/eurosenors/ |
| | 2024 ICEM – 26th International Conference for Electrical Machine
icem.cc/icem-2024-conference/ |
| 14–18 October | International Astronautical Congress (IAC)
iafastro.org/events/iac/ |

A-IQ Ready Consortium

Funding

A-IQ READY receives funding within the Chips Joint Undertaking (Chips JU) - the Public-Private Partnership for research, development and innovation under Horizon Europe and National Authorities under grant agreement n° 101096658.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Learn more about the project

